

Photoperoxidation of Anthracene Sulphonates

A. K. GUPTA, B. P. SINGH and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE*

Physical Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

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Oxygen quenching of excited singlet state of anthracene sulphonate (1-mono sulphonate (1AS), 2-mono sulphonate (2AS) and 1,5-di sulphonate (1,5AS)) and their photoperoxidation are studied in aqueous medium. Oxygen quenching constant is found to be nearly the same within the experimental error for different anthracene sulphonates. Theoretically calculated rate constant for oxygen quenching of fluorescence is compared with those obtained experimentally. However photoperoxidation is highly sensitive to number and position of the sulphonate group in the ring. The rate constant for peroxidation step is found to follow the order 1AS > 2AS > 1,5AS and involve singlet oxygen.

IN presence of oxygen, anthracene photooxidises most readily in solvents such as carbon disulphide, chloroform or bromobenzene where its fluorescence quantum yield is very low¹. In all these photooxidation reactions anthracene forms 1:1 transannular peroxides². It has been well established that the singlet excited oxygen ($^1\Delta_g O_2$) is the reactive species, a mechanism which was initially proposed by Kautsky in 1930³⁻⁵. With acceptors like aromatic hydrocarbons or cis-dienes, singlet oxygen behaves like a good dienophile and the reaction is similar to Diels-Alder addition. Anthracene is known to react with singlet oxygen as well as with other dienophiles whereas naphthalene is unreactive toward singlet oxygen and toward most potent dienophiles^{6,7}. The most direct evidence for participation of singlet oxygen has been provided by Corey and Taylor who generated $^1\Delta_g O_2$ by rf discharge in presence of anthracene and obtained anthracene peroxide as reaction product.

Nucleophilic as well as electrophilic substitution on anthracene ring is likely to change the oxidation potential of anthracene. This change is expected to be reflected in the efficiency of $^1\Delta_g O_2$ reaction with substituted anthracene⁸. It was considered of interest to study the effect of substitution of sulphonate groups at various positions of the anthracene ring on direct photooxidation reaction with a view to get a better understanding of its mechanism. The substitution makes the compounds water soluble and has profound effect on fluorescence⁹ and infrared spectra¹⁰ of the compounds although absorption spectra are only slightly perturbed.

Experimental

Anthracene 1-, 2-mono and 1,5-disulphonates were prepared by reducing corresponding anthraquinones with Zn-dust and 20% NH_4OH for 4-6 hrs. The products were treated with active animal charcoal to remove traces of anthraquinones and other impurities. Anthracene sulphonates were crystallized three to four times from water and obtained as sodium salt. The

ease of reduction of different anthraquinone sulphonates were in the order: anthraquinone-1,5-disulphonate > anthraquinone-2-mono sulphonate > anthraquinone-1-mono sulphonate.

Photochemical reactions were carried out in a specially designed cell immersed in a thermostat and kept in a dark room. Solutions were stirred during exposure and oxygen or air, as required by the experiment, was bubbled through it. Temperature was maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.5$. The stabilized light source was a 300-watt Hanovia type 507/7 Hg discharge tube contained in a blackened box with a window towards the reaction vessel. A Wood's glass filter was used to isolate 365 nm radiation. The OD were measured with a Beckmann DU Spectrophotometer model 4700. Ferrioxalate actinometry was done to standardise the light source. The fluorescence measurements were made with the Brice-Phoenix Universal Light Scattering Photometer Model 1000 Series. A high pressure mercury discharge lamp type AH-3, 85 watts with 365 nm filter was used as the exciting source and observations were made at 45° to the direction of incidence. The fluorescence spectra were measured in Beckmann spectrophotometer model DU 4700 with spectrofluorometer attachment.

Results and Discussion

Oxygen Quenching of Fluorescence: The Stern-Volmer oxygen quenching constant K_q is related to the rate constant for oxygen quenching k_3 by the expression $k_3 = K_q/\tau$, where τ is the actual lifetime of the fluorescent molecule in absence of oxygen and can be calculated from the knowledge of quantum yield of fluorescence ϕ_f^0 in deoxygenated solution and mean natural radiative lifetime τ^0 by the relationship $\tau = \tau^0 \phi_f^0$.

Since for anthracene-1-sulphonate and anthracene-2-sulphonate, the mirror image relationship does not hold, an expression due to Strickler and Berg¹¹ was used to

* nee' Rohatgi

measure τ^0 . The expression is :

$$1/\tau^0 = 2.88 \times 10^{-9} \frac{g_l n_f^3}{g_u n_a} \int \frac{F d\bar{\nu}}{\bar{\nu}^3} \int \frac{\epsilon d\bar{\nu}}{\bar{\nu}}$$

where n_f and n_a are the mean refractive indices of the solvent over the fluorescence and absorption bands, $F(\bar{\nu})$ is relative fluorescence quantum intensity at wave number ($\bar{\nu}$) cm^{-1} . For singlet-singlet transition $g_l = g_u = 1$. Here it is assumed that $n_f = n_a$. The values so calculated from the absorption and fluorescence spectra are given in Table 1. The quantum yield of fluorescence ϕ_f^0 were determined by using anthracene in benzene as the fluorescence standard under condition of equal optical densities. Assuming oxygen quenching of singlet excited state to be diffusion controlled process the quenching rate constant k_3 can also be calculated from the expression

$$k_3 = \frac{8RT}{2000\eta} \text{ (where } \eta \text{ is the viscosity of solvent, R the}$$

gas constant and T the temperature in Kelvin)

	r_A in Å	D_A in cm^2s^{-1}
Anthracene 1 sulphonate	4.27	0.64×10^{-5}
Anthracene 2 sulphonate	4.27	0.64×10^{-5}
Anthracene 1,5-sulphonate	4.63	0.59×10^{-5}

Knowing the molecular radius of oxygen $r_{O_2} = 2\text{Å}$, its diffusion coefficient $D_{O_2} = 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and assuming that $\sigma_{AB} = r_A + r_B$, k_3 is calculated and is given in Table 1 column 8.

Oxygen quenches the fluorescence of a large number of organic molecules. In most of the cases the quenching reaction step is diffusion controlled. Various types of interaction between O_2 and excited organic molecule are theoretically possible.

TABLE 1

Compounds	τ^0_{ns}	ϕ_f^0	$k_1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$K_q \text{ lM}^{-1}$	$k_3 \times 10^{-10} \text{ lM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	$k_3 \times 10^{-10} \text{ lM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Calculated)
1 ASO ₃ ⁻	13.7	0.25	7.3	2.2	150	4.2	2.6
2 ASO ₃ ⁻	11.8	0.40	8.4	1.3	200	4.2	2.6
1,5 A(SO ₃) ₂	14.5	0.26	6.9	2.0	190	5.0	2.8

The calculated value for aqueous solution at 30° works out to be $1.26 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The discrepancy between calculated and experimental value (Table 1) of k_3 may be due to larger sphere of quenching action than the collisional separation and also due to approximation inherent in the above equation. The failure of above equation in predicting the quenching rate constant apparently lies in the fact that Stokes-Einstein equation underestimates the diffusion coefficient of small molecule like oxygen. A better expression for rate constant of diffusion process is given as

$$k_3 = 4\pi N'(D_A + D_B)\sigma_{AB}$$

where N' is the number of molecules in millimole, D_A and D_B diffusion coefficients of reacting molecules and σ_{AB} the encounter distance. Estimation of molecular radius (r_A) of anthracene sulphonate from its molar volume, (calculated from its density) and substitution of r_A into the Stokes-Einstein equation, $D_A = kT/6\pi r_A \eta$, yields the diffusion coefficient of anthracene sulphonate in water.

From the observation of Parmenter and Rau¹³ that aromatic hydrocarbons are quenched by O_2 at the same rate regardless of singlet-triplet energy gap, it appears that mechanism (I) is probably not involved. Stevens¹⁴ has shown from kinetic studies that the mechanism (II) is the most important one for oxygen quenching of singlet excited state. Pulsed laser studies of Potashnick et al¹⁵ and of Tibilov et al¹⁶ also confirm the above view. Recently Stevens and Ors¹⁷ have shown that 9, 10 dimethylanthracene and rubrene which have high fluorescence yield, steps (I) and (II) are equally probable. However this is not the case with anthracene sulphonates which have low fluorescence yield and step (II) is the important one. For aromatic hydrocarbon the step (III) does not generally occur as ϕ_f and ϕ_{ISC} normally add up to unity, where ϕ_{ISC} is the quantum yield for intersystem crossing ($= \phi_T$)¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Photoperoxidation: Anthracene sulphonates are water soluble compounds. They undergo photodimerization in aqueous solution in absence of oxygen, just like the parent compound in benzene. When exposed

to sunlight in presence of dissolved oxygen quantitative conversion to endoperoxide is observed (Fig. 1). The absorption spectrum of photoproduct is similar to that obtained by Gillet²¹ for anthracene peroxide. The liberation of iodine on treating the irradiated solution with K¹I gives further support for peroxide mechanism²². The complete quenching of photoreaction on addition of NaN₃ indicates the involvement of O₂¹Δ_g since NaN₃ is a good quencher for O₂¹Δ_g²³. Works of Stevens¹⁴ on photoperoxidation and of Kawaoka et al²⁴ on theoretical study of oxygen quenching of organic triplet state reveals that oxygen quenching of triplet state leads to singlet oxygen formation

Fig. 1.: Absorption spectra for photoproduct obtained by exposing the 1 ASO₃⁻ solution to sun ray.

The various steps that can be visualized for the photochemical and photochemical processes occurring in the aerated solution of anthracene sulphonates can be represented as follows

From these steps, the quantum yield for photoperoxidation based on substrate disappearance assuming that photodimer formation is negligible under these conditions (the absence of photodimer in presence of oxygen is explained by the fact that O₂ quenches the excimer so that no dimer can be formed in its presence¹⁶) is given by the expression :

$$\phi_{AO_2} = \frac{k_6[A]}{k_6[A] + k_7} \times \frac{k_5[O_2]}{k_5[O_2] + k_4} \times \frac{k_2 + k_3[O_2]}{k_1 + k_2 + k_3[O_2]} \quad (1)$$

From spin statistical consideration, oxygen quenching rate constant for the triplet state k₅ should be 1/9 of the diffusion controlled rate¹⁴ and therefore k₅ ≈ 10⁹ M⁻¹s⁻¹. In oxygen saturated solution at atmospheric pressure [O₂] = 3 × 10⁻³ M. Taking k₄ to be of the order of 10³ s⁻¹²⁵, we have k₅[O₂] >> k₄. Hence k₅[O₂]/(k₄ + k₅[O₂]) ≈ 1. The factor (k₂ + k₃[O₂])/(k₁ + k₂ + k₃[O₂]) is triplet yield φ_T in presence of O₂. Eqn. (1) can be rearranged as

$$1/\phi_{AO_2} = 1/\phi_T + \frac{k_7}{k_6\phi_T} \times \frac{1}{[A]}$$

The plot of 1/φ_{AO₂} vs. 1/[A] for 1-ASO₃⁻ and 2-ASO₃⁻ gives k₇/k₆ and φ_T (Fig. 2, Table 2). φ_T calculated from k₁, k₂ and k₃ obtained separately from

Fig. 2.: Plot for 1/φ_{AO₂} vs. 1/[A]

- (A) 2 ASO₃⁻
- (B) 1 ASO₃⁻
- (C) 1.5 A(SO₃⁻)₂

TABLE 2

Compound	k_7/k_8 mole l^{-1}	$k_8 \times 10^{-7}$ $l. \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	ϕ_T (exp) $\frac{[O_2]}{= 3 \times 10^{-3} M}$	ϕ_T (cal)		ϕ_{AO_2} ; $[A]=10^{-4} M$	
				$\frac{[O_2]}{3 \times 10^{-3} M}$	$\frac{[O_2]}{6 \times 10^{-4} M}$	$\frac{[O_2]}{3 \times 10^{-3} M}$	$\frac{[O_2]}{6 \times 10^{-4} M}$
1 ASO ₂	0.92×10^{-2}	3.4	0.70	0.82	0.77	7.6×10^{-3}	7.0×10^{-3}
2 ASO ₂	1.1×10^{-2}	4.5	0.70	0.81	0.73	6.2×10^{-3}	5.9×10^{-3}
1,5 A(SO ₂) ₂	7×10^{-3}	0.7	—	0.85	0.76	1.2×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-3}

fluorescence measurement is in good agreement with the value obtained here. In case of 1, 5 A(SO₂)₂ inaccuracy in the measurement of ϕ_T from the intercept was avoided by using the calculated value of ϕ_T to get k_7/k_8 for this compound. There is very little [O₂] dependence of ϕ_{AO_2} , presumably due to small dependence of ϕ_T on [O₂] (Table 2). The oxidation of anthracene sulphonates are highly dependent on the number and position of the sulphonate groups. Sulphonate group is known to be an electron withdrawing group. So it shifts the oxidation potential of anthracene ring towards more negative value. k_8 agrees well with the reverse order of the ease of reduction of corresponding anthraquinone (see experimental) when k_7 is taken as $5 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

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